

NEW PARAMETER TO MODEL THE PERMEABILITY OF FIBER MATS

by

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ABSTRACT

Fiber mats are common reinforcements used in composites molding. Their permeability could be different even though their surface density and fiber diameter are the same. It is then necessary to define other characteristics to relate with the permeability.

In this work, a topological parameter, the overlaying density, is proposed for a better identification of fiber mats. It is based on the evaluation of the projected area, in the plane of the mat, occupied by the strands and on the variation of this projected area as a function of the number of single layers in the mat. For this, the mat is decomposed in several constitutive single layers. Then, a specific mean shape for the layout of the strands is determined for each mat. Based on this specific shape, a procedure to compute the overlaying density is developed. Results showing the variation of permeability as a function of the overlaying density are presented.

KEYWORDS: Resin Transfer Molding; Permeability; Mat; Fabric; Non Woven Reinforcement.

1. Introduction

Although continuous fibre mats are common reinforcements used in composites molding, no significant work has been concerned with their characterization in term of their permeability to the resin flow. They are usually characterized only by fibres diameter and surface density. In a previous work [1] we showed that the permeability of two mats could be significantly different even though their surface density and their fibres

diameter are the same. This does not come as a surprise and shows that other descriptive parameters are needed to characterize the structure of these reinforcements and to analyse the influence of that structure on their permeability.

In this work, a topological parameter for better identification of fiber mats is proposed. It is called the overlating density. It is based on the evaluation of the projected area, in the plane of the mat, occupied by the fibers and on the variation of this projected area as a function of the number of single layers in the mat. For this, the mat is decomposed in several constituent single layers. Also, a specific mean shape for the layout of the strands is determined for each mat. Based on this specific shape, a procedure, to compute the relative projected area resulting from the overlaying of the strands is developed.

2. Background

Filtration, in chemical processes and coalescers, as well as other applications, have been among the first applications of non woven continuous or short fiber mats. In the characterization for these applications, emphasis is made on the pore diameter in accordance with the capillary concept for fluid flow through porous media. In this way, in order to predict droplet capture, the fibers have been considered to be distributed in a regular pattern with their axis assumed perpendicular to the flow direction [2,3]. In practice non woven fiber mats have a random structure and any supposition that the fibers are parallel and regularly arranged is merely for mathematical and computation convenience.

Improvement of regular disposition of fibers was suggested [4,5]. In these cases random distribution is considered, but still suffers from the fact that the fibers are assumed to be parallel. In a recent study [6] the fibers distribution as well as their diameter are randomly distributed. Since the fibers in the mats are continuous, assumption that they fully cross the surface of computation is made. That study suggests a relation between the number of pores and the number of fibers in the layer. Also it gives a correlation between the mean pore area and the Kozeny approximation of the hydraulic diameter. The most important conclusion of the study is that the capture efficiency was found to depend on the number of layers, and so, on the free area of the fiber network. In fact, as one would expect, it shows that thicker network results in smaller free area.

The free area is the complementary area of the overlaying density of the material. Since the pore area is to be used in a way to determine the capture efficiency by summing all pores areas and since the number of pores may be related to the number of strands, the total free area may be used to characterize these materials especially for composites molding processes. The resulting free area is a consequence of the overlaying

pattern of the strands in the mat. The variation of the overlaying density as a function of the number of layers in a mat is a potential property that may represent more adequately the fibrous network. The purpose of this work, conducted for three types of fiberglass mat, is to explore this potential characteristic. In mat construction, strands made of several individual fibers or monofilaments (50, 100, 200, or more) are used. For the purpose of flow analysis one should refer to strand diameter instead of fiber diameter because during the filling process, the flow through each strand is likely to be insignificant if compared to the flow surrounding the strands which then become the basic shapes of the fibrous network.

3. Theory

The parameter calculated here is the overlaying density of the strands in the mat structure. It represents the net projected surface, in the plane of the mat, occupied by the strands (or inversely of the void fraction). This clearly depends on the strands pattern, dimension, position in each layer and also on the way the layers are superimposed. Figure 1 illustrates several situations that could occur, when two strands taken as rectangular cylinders are laid in a reference volume for which the same porosity will be calculated. It shows how the disposition of strands will affect the overlaying density which in turn affects the flow behavior in different directions of the elementary volume. In the first case (a), the total, in plane projected area, occupied by the cylinders is the same as for one cylinder. For the second case (b) this surface is larger while for the third case it is the largest one. However, the in plane free surface that an in plane flow can see through the network varies in the opposite direction as can be seen in the Figure.

Figure 1: Different situations of overlaying strands for the same calculated porosity in a control volume

This simple example illustrates how the overlaying density parameter may be of interest to predict permeability. To analytically determine the overlaying density of a non woven fiber mat the following approach is taken:

- The mat is decomposed in several single layers taken as constituent entities.
 - When the surface of reference considered is very small (microscopic concept), the strands axis may be assumed to be straight lines. In our macroscopic approach however, any assumption that the strands are straight becomes unrealistic and the real pattern of strands deposition should be taken into account. For this, in all single layers, the strands are taken in a given unique pattern (for example circular or sinusoidal).
 - Since mats are fabricated with strands, the strand diameter is taken as the characteristic diameter instead of the real fibre diameter. In this case the strands are taken to have a constant diameter d_r .
 - Within an elementary in plane square surface of side w the strands are laid in a unique shape, either circular or sinusoid with randomly distributed parameters. Figure 2 gives a schematic representation of the definition of the position for each pattern.
 - It is assumed that each layer of a given mat has the same mass density but not necessarily the same overlaying density.
 - Since the mass density of each single layer is constant, and as the length of each strand varies within the reference surface, the total number of strands $il(j)$ in each layer j may be different from one layer to the other.
- Following this, the projected area $Ap_{i,j}$ of the strand i from the layer j is obtained by:

$$Ap_{i,j} = d_r L_{i,j} \tag{1}$$

where $L_{i,j}$ is the length of the strand i,j and d_r is the mean diameter of the strands.

Figure 2: a)Disposition of fibers in strand.

b) an c) Definition of circular and sinusoidal patterns for strands

Common surface $Ac_{i,j}^{k,m}$ between the strand i of the layer j and the strand k of the layer m when they cross each other depends on the relative space position of each of the two strands and is computed for all strands k,m laid out before the strand i,j in order to obtain a resultant area $Ar_{i,j}$ which is the contribution of the strand i,j in the overlaying density following the expression :

$$Ar_{i,j} = Ap_{i,j} - \sum_{k=1, m=1}^{k=kl(m), m=j} Ac_{i,j}^{k,m} \quad (2)$$

were $kl(m)$ represents the total number of strands $il(m)$ in the $m - 1$ first layers and the $k - 1$ first strands in the layer m . Then Ao , the net projected surface of all the strands computed at this point is :

$$Ao = \sum_{i=1, j=1}^{i=il(j), j=jl} Ar_{i,j} \quad (3)$$

$il(j)$ is the total number of strands in the layer j while jl is the total number of layers . Then the overlaying density is obtained by :

$$Od = \frac{Ao}{w^2} \quad (4)$$

4. Simulation

As this has been mentioned before, the mat is reconstituted by superimposing several single layers up to the quasi total covering of the square surface of reference. Single layers are simulated by strands layout in a selected pattern. For this, one of the two basic shapes shown in Figure 2 can be chosen. With that shape a computer program reconstitutes the mat and calculates the overlaying density. The program flowchart is schematically shown in figure 3.

From the measured data, namely the mass of single layer M_l and the strand diameter d_r , the total number of strands $il(j)$ of each layer j is determined using the following equation:

$$M_l = \sum_{i=1}^{i=il(j)} \frac{\pi}{4} \rho_{gr} d_r^2 L_{i,j} \quad (5)$$

In this relation ρ_{gr} is the strands density and $L_{i,j}$ is the length of the strands i, j , computed from the parameters defining the strand coordinates in the surface of reference. Subroutines GGUBT and GGNML from IMSL have been used to obtain random values for the strands coordinates. The first one generates uniform distributions while the second one generates normal distribution.

The common projected surface of two strands is calculated following the occurring situation and is then subtracted from the total projected area of the strand. Then the resulting area, equation (2), is added to the cumulative projected area, equation (3), of the overlaid strand until this step. Computation is then continued up to a limit where no significant change can be obtained or when reaching the entire covering of the surface of reference. Two basic patterns were taken to analyze the three mats

considered here, a circular one which suit the mats OCF 8610 and U750, and sinusoid pattern for the NICO 758.

4.1 Circular Pattern : A circular strand i, j , is defined using the coordinates $x_{i,j}, y_{i,j}$ of the centre of the circle containing the arc, and the circle radius $r_{i,j}$ as shown in figure 2-a. The angle of the arc $\theta_{i,j}$ and the reference position $\phi_{i,j}$ of one of the ends are then deducted in such a way that only the portion of the circle contained in the surface of reference is taken. For this pattern, the centre of the arc may be positioned following a uniform distribution in the plane while the radius can be generated by a normal distribution. The figure 4-a. shows different possibilities of intersection of two circular strands. The more frequent situations are cases (c) , (f) and (e) , one or two intersections. In these situations the surface of intersection of two strands i, j and k, m is assumed to be a lozenge of side $\frac{d_r}{\sin(\alpha)}$ (see Figure 2-b) which is an approximation of the curved side of the surface. The angle α of the lozenge is deducted from the slopes $p_{i,j}$ and $p_{k,m}$ of the tangent lines to each arc at the point of intersection of the strands center lines using the equation:

$$\alpha = \left| \text{Arctg}(p_{i,j}) - \text{Arctg}(p_{k,m}) \right| \quad (6)$$

When the intersection is a complete lozenge the common area is obtained by:

$$Ac_{i,j}^{k,m} = \left| \frac{d_r^2}{\sin(\alpha)} \right| \quad (7)$$

In the situations (a), (b) and (d) of the same figure, the surface of intersection is a meniscus or a portion of it. For cases (a) and (b) the common surface is obtained by:

$$Ac_{i,j}^{k,m} = \left| \frac{1}{2} [r_{i,j}^2 (\delta_{i,j}^2 - \sin(\delta_{i,j})) - r_{k,m}^2 (\delta_{k,m}^2 - \sin(\delta_{k,m}))] \right| \quad (8)$$

and in the case (d) it is obtained by:

$$Ac_{i,j}^{k,m} = \left| \frac{1}{2} [r_{i,j}^2 (\delta_{i,j}^2 - \sin(\delta_{i,j})) + r_{k,m}^2 (\delta_{k,m}^2 - \sin(\delta_{k,m}))] \right| \quad (9)$$

4.2 Sinusoid Pattern : The sinusoid strand is defined by the position y , of its axis, in the vertical direction and the position x of its first maximum value in the horizontal direction. The amplitude as well as the wave length are obtained from measurements (see Figure 2-b). The surface of intersection of two strands is a function of the differences in phase Δx and Δy in both directions . This surface can be computed from the number of intersections and the area of two elementary surfaces approximated by lozenge shape. Here again the angle of the lozenge is deducted from the tangent lines to each strand at the intersection points of their center lines.

5. Overlaying Density Measurements

To determine an effective strand diameter and a the density of a single layer, samples from each mat were decomposed into several single layers that one may obtain without changing the pattern and the layout structure. These single layers have been taken as constituent entities for each mat. From these decomposed single layers, layout pattern has been determined. Strand diameter measurements have been carried out using an optical comparator and an average value was then obtained for each mat. Table 1 shows the characteristics of the three mats studied. Here ξ_i is the mat surface density; ξ_{sl} is the single layer surface density; d_r the average diameter of strands and finally the pattern in which the strands are laid out.

Table 1. Characteristics of the three mats studied.

<i>Mat</i>	$\xi_i (\frac{kg}{m^2})$	$\xi_{sl} (\frac{kg}{m^2})$	$d_r (\mu)$	<i>Pattern</i>
<i>OCF 8610</i>	0.300	0.020	70.5	<i>Circular</i>
<i>NICO 758</i>	0.450	0.008	30.3	<i>Sinusoidal</i>
<i>U 750</i>	0.665	0.021	105	<i>Circular</i>

Overlaying density measurements were carried out on an Image Analyzer using the decomposed samples with different numbers of single layers. Then the total projected area has been determined as a function of the number of layers. The total number of single layers in each sample was determined by comparing the surface density of a single layer with the the surface density of each sample. Since the strands are made of glass, special care was taken to increase the contrast between the strands and the void to improve the image quality. This has been acheived by using a dark surface to support the samples during measurements. The video camera used with the image analyzer was positioned in such a way that the measurements were carried out on a square surface of side 50 X 50 mm.

6. Results and Discussion

Figures 5 gives for each mat the comparison between the measured values for the overlaying density and the computed ones using the procedure previously described. From these plots, it can be seen that the agreement is reasonably good, especially when the number of layers is less than 8. We also notice that for a large number of layers, the model underestimates the overlaying density for the circular pattern, Figure 5 a) and c), and overestimates it in the case of the sinusoid pattern.

In a previous presentation [7], a flow model based on the drag forces around the strands and the shear forces on the cavity walls was suggested. Using that model

in conjunction with Darcy's law, the following theoretical expression was derived to calculate the permeability factor k of a given mat [8]:

$$\frac{1}{k} = \frac{\rho_{gr}}{\rho_g} \frac{N_{sl} O_d (1 + R_{Od})}{d_r H (2 - \ln(Re))} + 12 \frac{N_{sl} + 1}{\phi} \quad (10)$$

where ρ_g is the fibers density, ρ_{gr} the strands density, N_{sl} the number of single layers in the cavity, O_d the overlaying density of the single layer, R_{Od} the overlaying rate of strands in a single layer, d_r the strand diameter, H the thickness of the rectangular cavity, ϕ the porosity and Re is the Reynolds Number based on the strands diameter.

Figure 6 shows the computed values of the permeability as a function of the overlaying density of a single layer for the circular pattern which is the case for the mats OCF 8610 and U 750. This result indicates that the overlaying density is a suitable parameter to be included in a model for the permeability.

7. Conclusion

A new parameter called the overlaying density is suggested to help in the characterization of fiber mats structures. It is based on the net projected area of the strands of a given mat. A procedure to reconstitute the fibrous network and calculate the overlaying density was developed and a simulation for three mats was done using circular or sinusoidal basic shapes as approximation for the strands patterns. Random distributions of these basic shapes were used to simulate the construction of the mats. A good agreement was found between the calculated values for the overlaying density from the simulation with the experimental ones obtained with an image analyzer.

The effect of the overlaying density on the permeability indicates that it is appropriate to use this parameter in a model of the permeability for a non woven reinforcement.

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Biographical Note

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Figure 3: Procedure Flow chart

Figure 4: Possible intersections of circular strands

Figure 5 : Overlaying density for the three mats

Figure 6: Permeability as a function of the overlaying density